

Power Jewellery: Mediating Powers through Jewellery

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Abstract

“When I wear it, I feel it gives me life force.”

The quotation belongs to an 87 year-old woman who tells about her brooch which she got as an engagement gift from her future husband decades ago. The brooch is still giving her force to live. This paper is about the power people gain from their jewellery. It explores how people feel they gain powers through their pieces of jewellery. These powers seem to influence the way they desire things and how they appropriate their possessions. In this paper I will describe the beliefs that transform possessions into mediators of powers.

Conference theme: Value and Culture

Keywords: design, jewellery, power

The Power of Jewellery

People possess and wear jewellery for various reasons. The pieces of jewellery are not only artifacts for people to own and wear, but they also connect the possessors to their families and traditions. These connections become strong when people believe in them and cherish them. Later, as time goes by, the beliefs emerge as powers in jewellery. Although this paper describes only the emergence of the powers in jewellery, other objects can also act as power objects. For example, CDs the taxi drives place in rear-view mirror, the photographs people carry with them and wearables the football fans carry on game days are also objects that are believed to have powers (Belk, 1988, Paine, 2004, Lindquist, 2006). However, I will in this paper explore power in only one product category, pieces of jewellery.

In this article, I will explore the power of jewellery by applying anthropological studies from primitive societies to a Western society's ladies' jewellery. Emile Durkheim (1980) has studied the power of objects in the primitive cultures of North America and Australia. He describes the phenomenon of the emergence of the power by totemic values of the object. The totemic power is power from nature and society, and it is valid only when a group of people believe in it. According to Durkheim an object can only become a totemic object when the power of it is collectively believed in. In the cultures he has explored the societal groups that have totemic symbols are the clans. The power of the totemic object appears from the clan which it represents. The power the totemic object gives for its possessors is the supernatural power the clan has. By these totemic objects, the powers can be distributed to the members of the clan. According to Durkheim (1980), the power of the artifact is not owned by a possessor, but by the kinship where it effects on and in which it is believed in.

Building on Durkheim, anthropologist Marcell Mauss (1999) studied the spiritual qualities of things in archaic societies. His suggestion of spiritual things is that they have *hau* which is the spiritual power in the thing. Mauss' *hau* is similar to the power of jewellery, which also can be handed down with the artifact. An important aspect in jewellery emerging to power jewellery is its history. Jewellery are often got as gifts or inherited. Mauss' theory of gifts as objects of exchange is relevant when exploring the today's possessing of jewellery. Mauss discusses about the spirit of an item handed down to a new possessor via the artifact. When the item has a new possessor, the spiritual quality influences her life until she is obligated to give it onwards. Even though Mauss calls giving the return gifts as an obligatory gesture, I consider the return gifts in this study as practices of giving the same artifact onwards in the kinship.

Even though the anthropological studies I am exploring in this paper have been conducted within the primitive and archaic societies, the outcomes of those have been applied in modern societies. In particular, Russel W. Belk has explored possessed objects as extensions of the self (1988) in modern society. According to Belk's study, the possessors communicate with their possessions. The possessions, especially the inherited ones, carry the history of current and previous possessors. According to Belk, objects cultivate the possessor's awareness of the past. Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi and Eugene Rochberg-Halton have conducted a study of peoples' significant objects in urban environment (1981). Even though they studied peoples' possessions in urban modern society, they also addressed the importance of other people, in their study, the family, as an essential factor of objects becoming meaningful for people. The studies from primitive cultures do not affirm possessors' private thoughts meaningful, while the studies conducted in urban modern societies discuss not only about the collectiveness but also the privacy when valuing possessions (Boztepe, 2007, Walker, 2006, Holbraad, 2007). However, due to narrative data of my research, I will discuss in this article about private and collective level when powers merge into pieces of jewellery. I will explore how the exchange and collectiveness effect on biographies of jewellery in modern society.

Data and Methods

This article is based on literature of power objects and on narratives about people's significant jewellery. The narratives were gathered in Finland by the Kalevala Women's Association in 2007 by organizing a writing competition. The data consists of 699 freely written stories from the competition. The original purpose of the material has been to preserve narratives about Finnish cultural heritage. Since there were no further rules for the competition than the title of it, *Jewellery Speaks of Its Wearer*, the stories are rather versatile. There are poems, fables, lists of possessions and narratives of jewellery in everyday life. I studied further the 464 stories of peoples' jewellery in their everyday life. I decided to study only the stories written by women, since men's stories were not about their possessions. The authors were mainly old ladies of different backgrounds and professions. The best three stories were awarded with Finnish jewellery, and the finest 55 stories were published in an anthology.

I analyzed the selected stories by categorizing the contents by the frequent discoveries. One frequently recurred aspect was the power gained from jewellery. Gifts, meanings, ownerships, memories, and lost jewellery were also discussed often. Nevertheless, in this article I will explore further the power of jewellery. The power of the jewellery was discussed in 92 stories

which were again categorized by their contents. I noted that people described the power of their jewellery in two ways. The possessors have either experienced the power or acquired the power. Whereby, I consider the powers private and collective. The private, experienced powers can be either personal experiences or the experiences inherited as memories from the earlier possessors. These powers can be either abstract or concrete life assisting features that the jewellery provides. The collective powers that are learnt are of common knowledge, e.g. from traditions, folklore or brands. These stories of collective powers can be again divided into two categories, into abstract symbolizing powers, and into concrete curing powers (see table 1).

Private Experienced powers		Collective Acquired powers	
Jewellery provides (Abstract)	Jewellery assists in life (Concrete)	Jewellery cures when worn (Concrete)	Jewellery symbolizes (Abstract)
Happiness Connection to family Luck Hard luck Confidence Force Security Peace Joy Passion Wisdom Adavance Courage Will Life force Stamina Hope Protection from evil Protection from sorrow Protection from fear Protection for a child	In forgiving In yearning after someone In monetary problems Surviving in life Faith to the future	Gold cures the hearing Gold cures the eye disease Amber cures rheumatism The jingling drives away the evil spirits Provides long life Protects form the misfortunes	Fertility Honesty Vigorous womanhood Wellbeing Victory through misfortunes Keeping the promises Commitments over misfortunes Plaintiveness Femininity Love Perdurability

(Table 1.) Categories of the powers

Jewellery in these categories may be any kind of jewellery: mass produced, custom made, made out of precious material or not, cheap jewellery from a marketplace, significant heirlooms or souvenirs, etc. The appearance of jewellery does not actually matter in the process of it to become power jewellery. The beliefs, experiences and the history influence on the emergence of jewellery to become as power jewellery.

Emergence of the Power

People tend to develop attachments to their jewellery because they believe that jewellery have the powers people can gain. The powers jewellery mediates for possessors make peoples' lives better because people believe in them. The power gained from jewellery helps in unexpected situations, as well as cheering up everyday life. The power of the jewellery also helps people to reflect themselves in the reality of life since the powers are merged with the memories attached to the pieces of jewellery. The memories are normally built on the people and occasions linked to the possessors' history. There are several stories in which the memories are even older than the possessors themselves, since the pieces of jewellery are inherited.

“The story of my amber necklace starts beyond four generations. There was my grandmother’s grandfather, vicar Karl Gabriel Lyra (1786-1872), who was the possessor and the wearer of this necklace. He really wore the necklace to cure his rheumatism.”

Memories from past generations merge with the new possessor when she brings her own personal outlook to a piece of jewellery. Therefore, one memory does not mean the same to the mother as it does to the daughter. Even if the story of the memory is the same, each meaning of it is individualized by the possessor. For example, in this quotation about an amber necklace, the first possessor wore it to cure his illness, but for the current possessor after several generations, it stands as a memento of relatives.

“Sometimes I have worn the necklace a lot, of course depending on clothing and the occasion. Still, each time I’ve remembered its long story and all the people who also have worn it. It might not be monetary valuable; anyhow it is a memento and a rare object.”

Most of the stories of the power jewellery are about jewellery which has had earlier possessors. Therefore, the powers are inherited, as are the actual pieces of jewellery, and these powers have helped earlier possessors in their lives. The power may also be added later to the jewellery, when they are given to the next possessor, for example, to give happiness. And later jewellery turns out to be representation of happiness. Therefore, in later use it gives the power of happiness for the current possessor. Often the powers are merged from several persons' histories, either from the possessors or from persons somehow related to the histories of the jewellery. Hence, the powers are rarely built entirely on one person's experiences and memories. The emergence of the power of jewellery is similar to Durkheim's (1980) description

of the emergence of totemic objects; those are always representations of the constructs of the larger society's thoughts. As with in totemic objects, they are not truly powerful if a larger group of people do not believe in them; the powers of jewellery strengthen when the stories of the memories are handed down through the generations.

When the piece of jewellery has been worn at least once on an occasion when the possessor has felt that she gained power from it, it may become power jewellery. This does not yet mean that the piece of jewellery would be power jewellery. The power experienced has to be turned into the belief of power before the piece of jewellery can be power jewellery, possibly also for other people than the current possessor. The experience merges into the belief when its characteristics as belief become stronger by iterating the stories of the experiences to others, or by reviewing it in the possessor's mind. Hence, the experiences turn into beliefs which are mediated to new possessors in the form of memories (Koskijoki, 1997). Without the iteration the experiences stay as detached experiences, but when they are merged into the beliefs, the beliefs turn into invisible power features of the piece of jewellery. As features of the pieces of jewellery, the powers are tangible representations of the beliefs which can also be given onwards to new possessors. The piece of jewellery itself does not imply power, but the beliefs in power jewellery do imply powers.

(Table 2.) A formula of emergence of the power jewellery.

Transferring the power

Once jewellery has been transformed into power jewellery, the power feature stays in it. Therefore, the power can be transferred from the previous possessors to the new possessors. According to my data, transferring the power is thought of as an almost obligatory gesture in the biography of jewellery. If one has gained power from the piece of jewellery, the possibilities for

others to gain it also must be distributed within the family. The power of jewellery can be transferred to another person as well as to another piece of jewellery.

People usually add the power features unintentionally and unconsciously to their jewellery. They are not searching for occasions for their jewellery to merge into power jewellery, but the conversion just happens when there is an opportunity for it. Although the conversion from jewellery to power jewellery is not an intentional action, it happens when the possessor realizes that the piece of jewellery can be related to power occasions. This differs when considering gifts; then it is also possible that the giver loads the power into the jewellery by using the occasion for which the gift is given. For example, if the gift is given because of a birth, then later the possessor can think she gains e.g. happiness or joy from the piece of jewellery (see also Mattelmäki, 2006).

Belk (1988) describes possessions as containers in which people are able to store their memories and their feelings and with which people are also able to attach their senses of the past. He illustrates this with the example of souvenirs: “A souvenir may make tangible some otherwise intangible travel experience.” (Belk, 1988. pp. 148). Within the stories, there are several examples of pieces of jewellery which are souvenirs and, at the same time, power jewellery.

“The stone pendant reminds me of the cornerstone of life, of warmth, of power of forgiving, of connections to the surroundings and upwards. It is a reminder of finding the right place in the world.”

Belk (1988) describes products as links to possessors’ past, and, in my opinion, they are also links to products’ powers. As I have described above, these powers can be experienced only as effects from past occasions. The experiences of the jewellery shared with past generations strengthen the possibility of experiencing the power of the jewellery. Previous possessors’ experiences of jewellery play an important role in their emergence to power jewellery. The experiences could also be called as co-experiences, since they are collective (Battarbee, 2004). Even though the piece of jewellery is not worn together with the previous possessors, they still influence strongly the current possessors’ view of jewellery.

”Back then, the cross I got from my mother gave me some sort of a connection to my grandma, who I would’ve like to have known. I hope that grandma’s cross will in time remind my own daughters of Karelian women’s persistence, which will eventually turn even rough periods into good times.”

From person to person

In the stories of my data, pieces of jewellery are often received as gifts. These are either new products or ones handed down as onward going gifts. According to Mauss, who has studied the nature of gift exchange in archaic societies, giving a return gift is an obligatory gesture (1999). He also claims that the receiver of a gift does not only receive an artefact but also part of the giver's self and soul. In the stories, the gesture of giving a return gift inside the family is more versatile since the same piece of jewellery may be given as a return gift to a person of a next generation in the family. The piece may be given for the same occasion, for example the oldest daughter's graduation present will be given to her oldest daughter when she will graduate. When jewellery is given to a new possessor, it does not only include the artefact itself, but also the power the previous owner is willing to pass onwards. Jewellery which stay in family by this unwritten law of giving them onwards make them become even more significant since they have been able to soak up memories and experiences for a long time.

“Some day I want to give it to my own daughter and hope that she will pass it on to hers, and maybe the chain can continue even longer. One woman's happy moment could continue in a women's, mothers' memento throughout generations.”

The power can be mediated to the piece of jewellery also from the persons the possessor does not personally know. When a similar piece of jewellery has been worn by an admired person, the experienced power from her can be mediated to totally different, but alike, jewellery. The powers can also be gained from the culture or from the ancestors.

From Object to Object

Even though most of the jewellery is designed to last long, sometimes they get broken, or, significant jewellery might get lost. In cases of broken and lost power jewellery, people tend to give possibilities for the powers to be transferred to new or remodelled products. Often people tend to reshape their jewellery when something significant happens. Together with the significant occasion this reshaping also affects to the transformation of jewellery to end up as power jewellery. These changes in the appearance of jewellery stay as visual reminders for current and future possessors.

“After moving out from childhood home the ring brought nice memories from there to my mind. It also gave relief to sad and yearning moments. It was a memento of my kinship, since it was made of my mother’s melted engagement and wedding rings. It connected me to the chain of past generations. When growing up and maturing from parents, it started to mean to me, not only beauty but also durability and adulthood. The ring was an image of the safety of home.”

Supporting the Power

The current possessor does not actually own the power in power jewellery since she is expected to hand it down to the next possessor. Therefore, the ownership stands only on the physical artifact. This means that the power jewellery is owned by larger groups of people, e.g. kinships or families, similarly as Durkheim (1980) describes totems are owned by clans, not individuals. In the culturally traditional jewellery the owner may be an even larger community than family, it may be the whole culture, nation, or the ancestors. The current possessor possesses the power jewellery only for a moment of its biography. The power of the jewellery cannot be handed down to the next generation without the stories connected to it. Therefore, the current possessor has the responsibility to keep the power on in jewellery. She also has the responsibility of giving the piece of jewellery onwards to the next possessor. The current possessor will choose the next possessor and hand the piece of jewellery down to her together with the story of the power. In the stories, it is usually obvious who will be the next possessor. If, for example, the current possessor got it as a wedding gift from her mother, she will give it as a wedding gift for her daughter. In case she does not have daughter, she will have to find another suitable person, e.g. daughter in law, to carry the power onwards. Decisions of the future of the power jewellery are liable actions. Belk (1988) also discusses about the future of the significant artifacts. He points out the importance of taking under consideration the will of the receiver of the artifact. However, in the stories, the will of the receiver is not discussed, but it is rather kept certainty, that the pointed receiver is always willing to receive the piece of jewellery.

“In the 60’s, my mother got a silver pendant as engagement gift from her fiancé, who later became my father. Their marriage has lasted longer than three decades. It has been powerful, lively and has at times faced even major difficulties. My parents are committed to each other, since they have promised to stay together until the end. Now when they have become seamlessly merged with each other, I admire their calm

happiness. At the eve of my wedding day I got the same pendant from my parents. For me, it symbolizes perdurability, trust, and commitment over problems.”

Discussion

In this paper, I have shown that even in modern societies, people attach many types of powers to their jewellery. These powers are private, personally experienced or collective, learnt from culture. However, as discussed above in this initial, thematically oriented interpretation of the stories, all the experiences of powers are subjective, and can become valid only when possessors believe in them. Collective beliefs of jewellery are valid for societies, families or kinships, while private beliefs are valid only for the current possessor before they are handed down to the new possessor. As the powers of the totemic items Durkheim (1980) has explored, the power of the jewellery is an abstract feature which is based on the belief of its existence. The societies where people belong to, exist also without any totemic artefacts or representing products. The power jewellery in modern society, as well as the totemic items in primitive cultures work as mediators of the connection with person and society. They do not yet make the connection, because that is done by people, but they work as indications of the connection. Even though the theoretical approaches of power items are from primitive and archaic cultures, I have in this paper shown that they also apply when exploring jewellery in the modern society. Still, as has been tentatively shown above, the powers of jewellery are in constant change. They are not just based on collective traditional beliefs, but also on private beliefs emerged from subjective experiences.

Understanding the existence and emergence of the power in jewellery provides new prospects to the field of jewellery design. Even though the powers cannot be directly designed into the pieces of jewellery, the possibilities for powers to attach can be taken into consideration when designing jewellery. Products of precious materials are usually designed to last a long time. The designs do not normally follow the latest seasons in fashion, but usually follow more classic styles of the time. Also the technical solutions and the materials can be chosen so that the product may last decades or even centuries. This allows a rather long biography for jewellery. When designing custom made jewellery the designers consider the wanted powers to appear in the piece of jewellery. Also, mass produced items can be purchased with the purpose of them ending up as power jewellery. The mass produced jewellery do not, when purchased, have the powers in them, since the powers are subjective for the possessors and their kinships. The powers will be attached to the jewellery when those are linked to possessors. However, there is mass produced power jewellery in the market: the ones which are connected to the collective

powers of the cultures, e.g. crosses and horoscope pendants. According to my data, redesigning the jewellery is often done when the possessor changes. By reshaping an existing item the new possessors want to perpetuate memories. The opportunities for redesigning the old pieces of jewellery are not usually explicitly taken under consideration when designing jewellery. Nevertheless, it would be a great opportunity for jewellery designers to think about the opportunities of later redesigning the jewellery when designing new jewellery. Or, the designers could also take into consideration the possessors' opportunities of reshaping the jewellery by themselves, also discussing these opportunities with the customer. The design could encourage the possessor herself to chance the appearance of loved power jewellery.

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